

Relevance of Shorthand in Modern Days' Offices and Businesses: A Study of Nigeria's Public Sector Entities

Udomette Bright Emmanuel

Department of Accountancy, Dorben Polytechnic Abuja, Garam – Tafa, Niger State.

surfemmaudomette@yahoo.com; +234(0)8068160728

Abstract

This study intends to examine the relevance of Shorthand in modern days' offices and businesses and to investigate whether the course-area should be wiped off from the Office Management and Technology (OTM) curriculum. In order to aid this study, questions were put with primary data obtained using questionnaire as research instrument. Survey design with discourse was applied and data collected were modelled and analysed using regression tool of analysis. Sample size was fifty secretaries drawn from different offices in the Federal Secretariat Complex, Abuja. Findings revealed that most offices in the public sector do not undertake dictation and transcription, hence secretaries are not really put to their full potentials in modern offices. Besides, development of advanced devices and voice-to-text software made traditional secretarial role of note-taking inessential. Finally, it was revealed that Shorthand still remain relevant for note takings at meetings to complement advanced technologies especially as certain (AI) software would require much voice training and so may misrepresent some words which may even result to changing meanings to conversation which may be easily corrected with notes taken hence it should not be taken off the curriculum. More so, where such devices malfunctions, the secretaries backup notes become saving grace. The study therefore concludes that offices should embrace the full spectrum of digital technologies. However, it is recommended that office information technologists and secretaries should be further trained in shorthand skills in addition to modern office technological skills to be relevant in all office routine functions.

Keywords: Shorthand, Secretarial duties, office technology, digital technologies, modern office

1.0 Introduction

Technological advancement had led to a lot of paradigm shifts in business operations, office operations and administrative practices. According to Udomette (2011), every aspect of business operations has been fundamentally transformed as a result of the advent of modern Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and associated networks; and this has caused the archaic mechanistic organisations to be in a state of flux; thereby forcing modern managers to redefine the organisation objectives and job contents; restructure organisational processes such that would enhance healthier relationships between the business with its customers and associates.

Secretaries are one of the most needed employees in the offices as it is their duty to keep record of all documents and correspondences in the office, take down notes and transcribe them into acceptable documents and also handle the filing and indexing of office records or documents. The job of secretaries become more complex especially in the area of filing hence filing clerks were necessary to be of assistance. The private and confidential secretaries were attached to chief executives, managers and office administrators as their personal assistants to handle in addition to record-keeping and reception of visitors on behalf of their boss, such duties as taking down notes, including telephone conversations, transcribing such notes to the form appropriate for office manager's actions or decisions. This is mostly done via the typewriter which is now replaced with computer. The note taking skill is enhanced using Shorthand as a writing tool, or in some few cases, steno-typing.

Today, most offices are run by managers who are knowledgeable of the use of computer at least with PowerPoint or other Office Suite packages and the Internet to meet their daily need. This has caused most managers not to see the relevance of the secretaries not to mention dictating and its resultant shorthand writing. This has made few secretarial staff who are still "managed" by their boss to see shorthand as a "phased-out" tool, an out-dated practice no longer required in modern offices. But, is Shorthand not necessarily relevant in modern offices despite the emergence of the digital technologies?

But shorthand had been a source of livelihood for millions of people; a tool of communication and note-takings at meetings, conferences, offices, etc. Shorthand outlines could be transcribed immediately and in the future date. It makes note taking speedier, confidential to non-experts and with personalised outlines, even shorthand writers may not easily interpreted confidential reports coded for such purposes.

Upon the above essence of shorthand, it seems modern technological development has engulfed the shorthand practice and its relevance in the office and so its use is no longer required in all offices. As the questions may be put, should shorthand be excluded in the OTM curriculum in tertiary institutions? Are modern offices using shorthand as a tool for business communication? Are the services and skills of secretaries really necessary in today's businesses and offices? These are the main reasons behind this study.

The major objectives of this study are as follows:

- i) To examine whether or not Shorthand is still relevant in modern offices

- ii) To identify the areas that Shorthand remain useful in modern office functions
- iii) To identify those factors that contribute to reduced need for Shorthand in modern offices
- iv) To proffer possible suggestions to the application of Shorthand besides modern digital technologies

The following hypotheses were tested to guide the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relevance of Shorthand in the performance of modern office tasks in Nigeria's public sector entities.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Shorthand skills and the areas in which they are applied in modern offices within Nigeria's public sector.

H₀₃: Factors such as digital technologies, automation, and modern office tools do not significantly contribute to the reduced need for Shorthand in Nigeria's public sector offices.

2.0 Conceptual Framework

Shorthand is speedwriting technique. It was formally and originally named as Phonography and defined as the art of representing spoken sounds by character (Pitman, 1837). In Pitman New Era Shorthand, shorthand is defined as the art of representing spoken sounds by written signs. Fundamentally, therefore, shorthand can be defined as the art of writing spoken sound by written signs or symbols. Although there are other forms of Shorthand writing systems such as Gregg's and Sloan's shorthand, Pitman Shorthand tends to remain the most widely used system of Shorthand. Pitman Shorthand was introduced in 1837 by Sir Isaac Pitman with modifications or innovations across the years, first after the first fifty years of its introduction and in later years including PimanScript, New Era and Pitman 2000 in 1975; all in attempt to make the art easier to learn and understand (Lawal, et al, 2011; Pitman Instructor, 1971).

Shorthand is expressed in terms of symbols or signs to represent consonant sounds and vowel sounds; that is, every sound heard can be represented in Shorthand, be it English or local sound. Sir Isaac Pitman developed the system of shorthand (voiced writing) after an intensive study of the phonetic structure of the English language, hence, shorthand is purely phonetic – that is, representing words as they are sounded and not according ordinary

longhand spelling. One prominent scholar of Pitman Shorthand, Emily D. Smith with a speed of about 280 words per minute did an extensive research into word frequency in the English Language and invented the PitmansScript in 1968 based solidly on the theory of word, consonant and vowel frequency (Lawal, *et al* 2011).

There are twenty-four consonants, twelve vowels, and four diphthongs. Consonant sounds as defined by Professor Sweet (in Pitman’s Instructor) are “the result of audible friction or stopping of the breath or in some parts of the mouth or throat” and these are represented by strokes and curves usually referred to as ‘outlines’. They are classified into six classes namely:

Name	No. of outlines	Letters covered
i) Explodents: straight strokes	8	P, B, T, D, K, G, CH and J F, V, TH (θ e.g. think), TH (ð e.g. then),
ii) Continuants: Straight curves	8	S, Z, SH and ZH
iii) Liquids	2	R (up), R (down) and L
iv) Nasals	3	M, N, and NG
v) Coalescence	2	W and Y
vi) Aspirate	1	H (up); H (down)

Shorthand Consonants. (Source: Pitman’s Instructor, 1971)

Vowels, on the other hand, are defined in Pitman Instructor as by Professor Sweet as: “if the mouth-passage is left so open as not to cause audible friction, and voiced breath is sent through it, we have a vowel”. In other words, vowels are sounds produced when the mouth-passage is left so open not primarily to cause audible friction with voiced breath sent through it. The twelve pure vowels are classified into six groups of long vowels and short vowels. The long vowels are represented by thick dots and dashes while the short vowels are represented by light dots and dashes. These vowels are majorly six groups of long and short variations as in:

	Long	Example	Short	Example
i)	a (a:)	balm	a (a)	Back
ii)	e (e:)	pay	e /e/	Debt
iii)	I or ee (i:)	bee	I (i)	Tit
iv)	aw (ɔ:)	tall	ō (^)	Top

v)	Ô	foe	û	Tub
vi)	ōō (U:)	food	öö (u)	Book

Shorthand Vowels (Source: New Era)

However, double-vowel sounds, popularly known as diphthongs also exist. They are vowel sounds that produce two vowels at the same time as in fine, buy, boy, toy, few, due, out, tout.

There are also triphones, three-vowel sounds. This is produced by additional vowel sound to the diphthongs as in tower, dying, loyal, voyage, issuing, towel, bowel, etc.

The beauty of shorthand is linked to its positional writing. This is linked to the vowels or diphthong sounds. There are three places alongside a stroke in which vowels may be written- beginning (first place), middle (second place) and end (third place) positions. In this regard, vowels (i) and (iv) above fall under first place written above the line, (ii) and (v) fall under second place written on the line while (iii) and (vi) are in third place written through the line.

All first place words are written above the line for example: car; back; law; call, etc. also, diphthong /ai/ and /aw-i/ are first place words e.g. time, boy, toy, lime, prime, etc

The second place outlines are written on the line and these covers vowels (e) and (o) as in load, toad, tub, thumb, led, fred, stay, day, stray, etc.

Diphthongs (iu) and /au/ and vowels (u) and (ee) are third place and are written through the line; examples few, duty, how, town, fee, tea, business, broom, etc. This unique feature of positional writing makes Pitman Shorthand different from other forms of Shorthand, which may be easily written on plain sheets but Pitman Shorthand requires lines, hence the need for Reporters Notebook.

Also fascinating is the fact that words are not written as spelt but as pronounced hence business is pronounced and represented as business /biz,niz/, balm /bahm/, but silent 'r' are represented in Shorthand except in few cases for instance, car is shown as /kahr/.

Generally, shorthand writing enhances speed; requires dedication and commitment, focus and concentration. Continuous development and daily drilling practice are basic requirements (National Secretarial Examinations Board, NSE 2021; Pitman New Era, Lawal, et al, 2011). According to the Pitman's Instructor, satisfactory progress in acquiring the art of Shorthand and the secret of success in Shorthand will only be achieved if certain portion of time is

regularly dedicated to the study each day. In other words, the knowledge, speed and skill of Shorthand can only be developed and achieved through constant and careful practice.

Why Shorthand is still necessary in most modern offices?

Okoth (2020) has asserted that Shorthand remains relevant today because it enables fast, efficient note-taking, especially in fields that require capturing information in real time such as journalism, court reporting, business meetings, and academic research. It also improves accuracy and reduces reliance on digital devices in situations where typing or recording is impractical.

Several empirical studies, however, have studied the declining use of Shorthand in modern administrative settings. Adebayo (2019) found that although technological tools such as digital recorders and transcription software have reduced the frequency of manual notetaking, many entities still rely on Shorthand for minute-taking during confidential meetings. Similarly, Eze and Nwosu (2021) reported that Shorthand remains relevant in contexts where real-time accuracy is critical and where technology may fail or misinterpret speech.

Research on office technology adoption has also highlighted the shift from traditional secretarial duties to ICT-driven roles. Ojo and Ogunyemi (2020) revealed that the introduction of automated office systems significantly diminished reliance on manual transcription, thereby reducing the prominence of Shorthand in daily tasks. However, they noted that organisations still expect secretaries to possess foundational Shorthand skills as backup documentation methods. This finding supports the hybrid skill model increasingly advocated in administrative studies.

Other studies have emphasised the relationship between technological change and skill displacement. For example, Igwe (2022) observed that digital transformation in public offices often leads to the substitution of manual administrative skills with automated solutions, but the shift is not always complete. Secretaries in his study expressed concern over device failure, data loss, and speech-to-text inaccuracies, reinforcing the continued pedagogical and practical relevance of Shorthand. This suggests that technological substitution does not equate to total redundancy. Although infrequently used, shorthand as a tool of reporting still remains relevant.

In the Nigerian context, empirical studies consistently report mixed perceptions regarding the future of Shorthand. Oladipo and Hassan (2020) found that while younger office personnel prefer digital tools, senior administrative officers still value Shorthand for its speed and clarity during meetings. The authors concluded that Shorthand retains contextual importance, particularly in public-sector settings where bureaucratic procedures demand accuracy and documentation integrity. Their findings align with the descriptive results of the present study.

Finally, studies evaluating curriculum relevance have argued for retaining Shorthand as part of office education. Nwachukwu (2021) demonstrated that institutions offering Office Technology and Management programmes consider Shorthand an essential foundational skill despite reduced usage. Respondents in the study emphasised the importance of Shorthand as a safeguard in technologically constrained environments. This mirrors the implications of the current research, which supports maintaining Shorthand as a complementary skill rather than eliminating it entirely.

3.0 Materials and Methodology

This study employed survey design with the use of questionnaire as primary data collection instrument and purposive sampling used to randomly select sample size of 50 secretaries from different offices at the Federal Secretarial Complex, Abuja. The survey research design was appropriate for collecting opinions and perceptions from individuals directly involved in office operations, thereby enabling the researcher to obtain first-hand information on the relevance of Shorthand in modern offices.

The structured questionnaire was designed on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) to measure three main constructs: perceived relevance of Shorthand; areas where Shorthand remains useful and factors contributing to the reduced need for Shorthand

Both descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) and inferential statistics (multiple regression analysis) were used, to summarise respondents' perceptions of Shorthand and to test the three null hypotheses, examining whether Shorthand relevance was significantly influenced by useful office areas or reduction factors respectively.

All statistical tests were performed at a **0.05 significance level** in line with established guidelines.

4.0 Results and Findings

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Relevance	2.84	0.65	1.63	4.30
Areas-Useful	3.21	0.52	1.63	4.14
Reduction-Factors	3.45	0.77	1.96	5.00

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 above has shown that Secretaries reported a *moderate level of perceived relevance of Shorthand* (M = 2.84, SD = 0.65). Ratings for *areas where Shorthand remains useful* were slightly higher (M = 3.21, SD = 0.52). Respondents also reported *significant presence of factors reducing the need for Shorthand* (M = 3.45, SD = 0.78), suggesting that modern digital tools and automation are strongly perceived as substitutes.

2. Testing the Hypotheses (Regression Analysis)

The regression model was: **Relevance = $\beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Areas-Useful}) + \beta_2(\text{Reduction-Factors})$**

Table 2: Regression Results

Predictor	β	t	p
Areas - Useful	0.11	0.60	.55
Reduction - Factors	-0.08	-0.61	.54

R² = .020

F(2, 47) = 0.48, p = .62

Model is **not statistically significant**.

Source: Author' Computation, 2025

The regression model showed that neither Shorthand relevance nor its predictors were statistically significant ($p > .05$). Thus, H_{01} (*There is no significant relevance of Shorthand in the performance of modern office tasks*) is retained. By this outcome, it implies that there is no statistically significant evidence that Shorthand plays a major role in influencing modern office performance in public-sector entities. This aligns with Ojo and Ogunyemi (2021) whose finding revealed that dictation and transcription are rarely practised today due to presence of automated systems.

Furthermore, the study showed that there are areas in which Shorthand remains useful did not significantly predict perceived relevance ($\beta = 0.11$, $p = .55$); thus H_{02} (*There is no significant relationship between Shorthand skills and the areas/functions where they are used*) is retained. Thus, it could be stressed that although Shorthand is still used in some office areas (e.g., minute-taking), these areas do not significantly influence the overall perception of its relevance.

Thirdly, the study revealed that factors (e.g., voice-to-text software) did **not** significantly predict perceived relevance ($\beta = -0.08$, $p = .54$). Thus, H_{03} (*Factors such as digital technologies, automation, and modern tools do not significantly contribute to the reduced need for Shorthand*) is retained. This implies that while respondents perceive modern technologies as reducing the need for Shorthand, statistically the relationship was not strong enough to reach significance in this sample of 50. Thus the study aligns with Igwe (2022) that modern digital technologies or digital transformation in public offices often leads to the substitution of manual administrative skills with automated solutions. It therefore follows that while advanced devices reduce the need for manual shorthand, Shorthand still provides important backup when AI tools fail or misinterpret speech.

The empirical results show weak statistical relationships, suggesting that although Shorthand is less central in modern digital offices, its complete irrelevance cannot be statistically validated. This supports the qualitative findings that Shorthand is less used, but remains helpful for accurate minute-taking, especially when AI voice-capture tools malfunction or misinterpret words. Thus, Shorthand should not be wiped off the OTM curriculum but retained as a complementary skill.

5. Discussion of Findings

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relevance of Shorthand in modern-day offices and businesses within Nigeria's public sector, particularly in the context of rapid technological advancement. The findings provide useful insights into how Shorthand is currently perceived, the areas in which it may still be useful, and the factors that have contributed to its declining application.

Descriptive results indicate that respondents generally rated the relevance of Shorthand at a moderate level ($M = 2.84$), suggesting that although Shorthand is no longer as dominant as it once was, it has not entirely lost value in office communication. This aligns with earlier observations noted in the abstract, where it was revealed that many public-sector offices no longer rely heavily on dictation and transcription, two activities for which Shorthand was traditionally indispensable. The lower relevance rating corroborates the view that secretaries in modern offices are not often engaged in the full spectrum of traditional secretarial duties.

Contrary to expectations, the inferential analysis showed that neither the areas where Shorthand is still applied nor the factors believed to reduce its need significantly predicted its perceived relevance ($p > .05$). This suggests that while respondents recognize both functional areas and modern substitutes (such as voice-to-text software), these factors do not, in practice, determine how relevant Shorthand is considered in their professional settings. One likely explanation is that although digital tools have become dominant, they have limitations—especially related to speech recognition errors, accent misinterpretation, and occasional device malfunction. As such, Shorthand remains a valued backup method for ensuring accuracy, particularly in sensitive meetings or when technology fails.

Furthermore, the finding that reduction factors (e.g., automation and digital transcription devices) were not significant predictors of perceived relevance implies that Shorthand's decline is more nuanced than simply being replaced by technology. Rather, respondents may perceive Shorthand as a skill that, while not frequently used, still serves a critical complementary role. This supports the assertion that Shorthand should not be completely removed from the Office Technology and Management (OTM) curriculum. Instead, the skill may remain relevant for special circumstances where reliability, confidentiality, and accuracy are essential.

Above all, the study's findings reinforce a balanced perspective: modern technologies undeniably reduce the routine dependence on Shorthand, but they do not eliminate the need for human-driven note-taking. Shorthand continues to provide value as a safeguard against technological imperfections, and its role in ensuring clarity and accuracy during official documentation remains a compelling justification for its retention in educational programs and modern administrative practice.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The empirical results have shown weak statistical relationships, suggesting that although Shorthand is less central in modern digital offices, its complete irrelevance cannot be statistically validated. Based on this fact, the findings reveal that although Shorthand is no longer widely practised in modern offices, partly due to the adoption of digital technologies and automation, its perceived relevance has not been completely eliminated. The regression results showed no statistically significant relationship between perceived relevance and either (a) areas where Shorthand is still used or (b) factors reducing its need. This means that while respondents acknowledge reduced reliance on Shorthand, they do not consider it entirely irrelevant. The study therefore concludes that Shorthand still holds complementary value in modern-day offices, particularly for accurate minute-taking and as a reliable alternative when digital recording devices malfunction or misinterpret spoken communication. Consequent upon the highlighted outcomes, the study made the following recommendations:

- i. Shorthand should not be removed from the Office Technology and Management (OTM) curriculum but retained and should be taught as a complementary or support skill that complements modern technologies during meetings and official dictations.
- ii. Secretaries should receive periodic training that integrates traditional shorthand with digital transcription tools, including the cloud shorthand software/apps, enabling them to function effectively in hybrid office environments.
- iii. Where confidentiality, accuracy, or device failure risks are high, Shorthand should be encouraged as the preferred documentation method to prevent loss or misinterpretation of vital information.
- iv. Public-sector offices should develop internal guidelines that require manual note-taking backup during meetings to complement audio or AI-based digital recordings, while retaining confidentiality of records in highly sensitive environments.
- v. Educational institutions and professional bodies should explore modernized versions of Shorthand, focusing on speed, simplicity, and integration with digital documentation systems

References

- Adebayo, T. M. (2019). *Assessment of shorthand relevance in contemporary administrative practices*. *Journal of Office Management Studies*, 14(2), 45–57.
- Eze, C. P., & Nwosu, O. J. (2021). Shorthand competence and workplace efficiency among secretarial staff in public organizations. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 8(1), 112–124.
- Igwe, K. C. (2022). Digital transformation and the perceived displacement of traditional secretarial skills in Nigerian public service. *African Journal of Management and Technology*, 10(3), 74–89.
- Lawal, Ezeah, Yaro, Agbassi & Akindele, (2011). *Longman Business Studies for Junior Secondary Schools, Bks1-3*; Longman
- National Secretarial Examinations Board (2021). The role of shorthand in modern days“ business. Examination Question
- Nwachukwu, E. O. (2021). Curriculum relevance of shorthand in Office Technology and Management programmes. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education*, 5(4), 88–97.
- Ojo, A. S., & Ogunyemi, B. O. (2020). Influence of office automation on secretaries“ use of manual transcription skills in modern workplaces. *Journal of Administrative and Information Technology*, 6(1), 59–70.
- Okoth, R. (2020). *The continuing relevance of shorthand in modern communication*. *Journal of Communication Studies*, 12(2), 45–53.
- Oladipo, S. A., & Hassan, M. T. (2020). Perceptions of shorthand usage among administrative officers in Nigerian ministries. *West African Journal of Applied Management*, 3(2), 101–115.
- Pitman, I. (1971). *Pitman Instructor*. Pitman
- Pitman, I. (1976, 1991). *New Era Pitman Shorthand, New Course (Reprints)*. Pitman
- Udomette, B. E. (2011). *Basics of Management Information System*. Sigma & Starlife Concepts